

Short communication

First record of *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Gastropoda; Ranellidae) found on the coast of Montenegro: notes about the range of the species

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Summary. We report the finding of two empty shells of the Ranellidae species *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) on the coast of Čanj, Montenegro. Although we cannot exclude that this may be the result of inadvertent human transport, these findings are of interest because this species has not been recently reported in the Adriatic Sea.

Keywords: *Cabestana cutacea*; Montenegro; south-east Adriatic Sea.

INTRODUCTION

Cabestana cutacea (Linnaeus 1767) is a Ranellidae species wide-spread in the Western Mediterranean (Ghisotti and Melone, 1968; Settepassi 1970; Saunders 1980) and along the Atlantic coasts of Africa and Europe, from Senegal north to the Channel Islands (Jeffreys 1863; Fischer 1865; Locard 1886; Nobre 1938; Saunders 1980; Fretter and Graham 1981; Rolan Mosquera 1983; Trigo and Otero Schmitt 1987; Ruscoe 2007). However, the most northern findings are probably attributable to occasional settlements of veliger in particularly hot summers and do not indicate permanent populations (Saunders 1980). It has also been found in the Atlantic islands of Madeira, Canary and the Azores (Nobre 1937; Nordsieck and Garcia-Talavera 1979; Poppe and Goto 1991; Moro et al. 2003; Bacallado et al. 2008; Segers et al. 2009).

Although it is not very common elsewhere, there are numerous reports, old and new, for the Western Mediterranean, showing that there are at present stable and viable populations. In particular, there are countless reports of the species from the Italian regions on the Tyrrhenian Sea.

Although by no means exhaustive, here we present records known to us for the Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 1). In the western Mediterranean, *C. cutacea* was reported several times for Morocco, Algeria and southern Spain, while most of the data come from the western coast of Italy (Tyrrhenian

and Ligurian Sea, coast of Sardinia and Sicily), followed by the coast of France and northern Spain. In addition, the first author of the present work has personally found this species in various localities in northern and eastern Sardinia–Italy (Stintino, Santa Teresa, Cala Liberotto), and these data are presented in Fig. 1. as “Doneddu-personal observations”.

Despite its spread and relative abundance in the western Mediterranean, *C. cutacea* has only very rarely been reported in the central and eastern Mediterranean. There are two reports from the Ionian Sea: Taranto–Puglia, Italy (Settepassi 1970), Porto Cesareo–Puglia, Italy (Trono 2006); one from Malta (Cacchia et al. 1993); and two for Aegean Sea: Cyprus (Ozturk et al. 2003), Messina–Greece (Fischer 2005; Koukouras 2010) (Fig. 1). Regarding the Adriatic Sea, Costa (1829) wrote generically „found in Adriatic“, without specifying any locality. Coen (1937) reports a finding from “the Italian coast of the Southern Adriatic Sea” and again no specific information was provided. There are no other data available since 1937, in particular this species is not mentioned in specific works concerning the malacological fauna of Montenegro (Stjepčević 1967; Stjepčević and Parenzan 1980) or in general of the Middle and Southern Adriatic (Cossignani et al. 1992; Dhora 2009). *Cabestana cutacea* is not even mentioned for the Adriatic Sea in the “checklist of Italian marine animal species” (Oliverio 2008). Thus we consider it interesting to report this new record, as a contribution to the present knowledge of the malacological fauna of Adriatic Sea.

Figure 1. Distribution of *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Gastropoda; Ranellidae) in the Mediterranean Sea.

Location	Reference	No.	Cette dans l'Herault	Locard 1886	14
Acitrezza, Italy	Mannucci 1983	40	Circeo, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Ajaccio, France	Payraudeau 1826	16	Circeo, Italy	Cossignani and Ardovini 2011	24
Ajaccio, France	Requien 1848	17	Civitavecchia, Italy	Smriglio et al. 1989	26
Alboran, Spain	Salas and Luque 1986	3	Cyprus	Ozturk et al. 2003	50
Algeciras, Spain	Aartsen et al. 1984	8	Elba, Italy	Settepassio 1970	23
Alghero, Italy	Aversano et al. 1984	42	Formia, Italy	Settepassio 1970	23
Alghero, Italy	Doneddu and Manunza 1989	43	Gaeta, Italy	Cossignani and Ardovini 2011	24
Almeria, Spain	Ballesteros et al. 1986	5	Garraf, Spain	Giribet and Peñas 1997	10
Anzio, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Genoa, Italy	Sorbi and Terzer 1982	21
Argentario, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Hyerès, France	Locard 1886	14
Baix Camp, Spain	Tarruella Ruestes and Lòpez Soriano 2006	9	Imperia, Italy	Rebora 1986	19
Bonifacio, France	Requien 1848	17	Naples, Italy	Toscano and Cretella 1991	69
Bosa, Italy	Miari and Graziani 1984	44	La Spezia, Italy	Tapparone-Canefri 1869	20
Brindisi, Italy	Oriolo 1974	62	La Spezia, Italy	Lugli et al. 1984	68
Cagliari, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Levanzo, Italy	Giannuzzi-Savelli et al. 1996	37
Cagliari, Italy	Giannuzzi-Savelli et al. 1996	37	Liguria, Italy	Jeffreys 1856	61
Cala Liberotto, Italy	Doneddu, personal data	47	Livorno, Italy	Appellius 1869	22
Calvi, France	Payraudeau, 1826	16	Livorno, Italy	Bertozzi et al. 1984	67
Campania, Italy	Berardelli et al. 1982	63	Malaga, Spain	Sabelli and Spada 1978	7
Campania, Italy	Cuomo et al. 1983	64	Malta	Cachia et al. 1993	49
Campania, Italy	Cossignani and Ardovini 2011	24	Maratea, Italy	Perretti 1984	33
Capo Miseno, Italy	Albanesi 1968	56	Marettimo, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Capo S. Vito, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Marseille, France	Locard 1886	14
Capri, Italy	Federico and Tripodi 1967	28	Martigues, France	Vial 1988	15
Capri, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Mataro, Spain	Ghisotti and Melone 1968	6
Capri, Italy	D'Angelo and Gargiullo 1978	29	Messina, Italy	Micali et al. 1987	38
Catalonia, Spain	De Chia 1912	12	Messina, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Catania, Italy	Philippi 1836	35	Messinia, Greece	Fischer 2005	51
Catania, Italy	Scuderi 2000	39	Messinia, Greece	Koukouras 2010	52
Catania, Italy	Cossignani and Ardovini 2011	24	Morocco	Pallary 1920	1

Morocco	Pasteur-Humbert 1962	2	Sagone, France	Payraudeau 1826	16
Naples, Italy	Bellini 1929	27	Saint Florent, France	Payraudeau 1826	16
Naples, Italy	Ghisotti and Melone 1968	6	Salerno, Italy	Berardelli and Fasulo 1988	32
Naples, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	San Tropez, France	Locard 1886	14
Napoli, Italy	Scacchi 1836	66	Sant Pol de Mar	Altimira 1977	11
Nice, France	Locard 1886	14	Sant Raphael	Locard 1886	14
Oran, Algeria	Pallary 1900	1	Santa Manza, France	Payraudeau 1826	16
Oristano, Italy	Silesu and Sosso 1987	45	Santa Teresa, Italy	Doneddu, personal data	47
Palermo, Italy	Philippi 1836	35	Scandola, France	Merella et al. 1994	18
Palermo, Italy	Mannucci et al. 1983	36	Scauri Latium, Italy	Facente et al. 1983	25
Palermo, Italy	Giannuzzi-Savelli et al. 1996	37	Scilla, Italy	Vazzana 2010	34
Palermo, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Sicily, Italy	Maravigna 1839	57
Palo Laziale, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Sicily, Italy	Negra and Lipparini 2005	59
Porto Cesareo, Italy	Trono 2006	48	Sicily, Italy	Costa 1829	65
Porto Empedocle, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Sicily, Italy	Aradas and Benoit 1870	58
Porto Torres, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23	Siracusa, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Possilipo, Italy	Albanesi 1970	30	southern Sardinia, Italy	Spano et al. 2002	46
Procida, Italy	Soppelsa et al. 2007	55	Spain	Hidalgo 1917	60
Procida, Italy	Ghisotti 1978	31	Stintino, Italyw	Doneddu, personal data	47
Provance, France	Settepassi 1970	23	Taranto, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Provance, France	Risso 1826	53	Tonnara, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Provance, France	Locard 1892	54	Torre Astura, Italy	Settepassi 1970	23
Provance, France	Locard 1892	54	Trapani, Italy	Lugli and Palazzi 1987	41
Punta Chullera, Spain	Luque 1986	4	Ustica, Italy	Giannuzzi-Savelli et al. 1996	37
Roussillon, France	Bucquoy et al. 1882	13	Valinco, France	Payraudeau 1826	16
Roussillon, France	Locard 1886	14	Čanj, Montenegro	new data	

DISCUSSION

Two empty shells of the Ranellidae species *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) were found beached on the coast of Montenegro, both at Čanj. In one of the two specimens, traces of the periostracum were still present. The shells were collected by students of the University of Novi Sad during a marine field trip course. The first specimen was collected in May 2010. (N 42° 08' 58.96" E 19° 00' 08.72") and the second two years later, in May 2012. (N 42° 09' 38.43" E 18° 59' 41.17") (Fig. 2). They are deposited in the collection of the Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad (Serbia).

Čanj is a small area of exposed beaches about 1500 meters long, mainly composed of gravel and coarse sand, surrounded by rocky coast; the sea-bottom in front is sandy, with the presence of seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa*.

Cabestana cutacea, whose size range from 32 to 105 mm (Settepassi 1970), is the less common of the Mediterranean Ranellidae (excluding *Cabestana dolaria* (Linnè 1767), which is probably only an Atlantic species, whose few Mediterranean reports are questionable), and seems to have become more uncommon than in the past, but the reasons for its decline are unclear. It is not likely threatened by excessive

collection because of its habitat: it is a species which inhabits rather deep water, 25-160 meters, but exceptionally can also be found in shallow waters (Sabelli and Spada 1978); where most of the known specimens have been found incidentally in fishing nets, or beached after storms. Saunders (1980) attributes the decline of this species to climate change, but this explanation seems unconvincing.

Fishermen, while cleaning their nets, often throw such shells back into the sea, and these specimens can be later found in localities far from where they actually lived. Both specimens from Čanj were found beached, one mixed with gravel and the other in a rock crevice, with no traces of soft parts; so we cannot exclude the possibility that they were inadvertently translocated by local fishing nets. However, along the coast around Čanj there are no big ports frequented by fishing vessels, and few local fishermen use small fishing boats in the surrounding area. For these reasons, the specimens of *C. cutacea* here described can be considered autochthones with sufficient probability.

Figure 2. *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) collected in Čanj (Montenegro, South East Adriatic Sea).

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REFERENCES

- Aartsen JJ, Menkhorst HPMG, Gittenberger E. 1984. The Marine Mollusca of the Bay of Algeciras, Spain, with general notes on *Mitrella*, *Marginellidae* and *Turridae*. *Basteria*, Supplement, No. 2: 1–135.
- Albanesi O. 1968. Itinerari malacologici campani: da Monte di Procida a Capo Miseno. [Malacological itinerary of Campania: from Monte di Procida to Capo Miseno]. *Conchiglie*. 4(3-4):46–49. Italian.
- Albanesi O. 1970. Appunti su alcuni ritrovamenti malacologici nel mare di Posillipo (Golfo di Napoli). [Notes on some malacological records in the Posillipo Sea (Gulf of Naples)]. *Conchiglie*. 6(5-6):35–37. Italian.
- Altmira C. 1977. Fauna malacológica marina de Sant Pol de Mar (Litoral N de la provincia de Barcelona). Primera parte. [Malacological marine fauna of Sant Pol de Mar (Litoral N of the Barcelona province)]. *Miscelànea Zoològica*. 4(1):23–32. Spanish.
- Appelius FL. 1869. Le conchiglie del Mar Tirreno. Parte seconda. [The shells of Tirrenian Sea. Second part]. *Bullettino Malacologico italiano*. 2(4):124–141. Italian.
- Aradas A, Benoit L. 1870. Conchigliologia vivente marina della Sicilia e delle Isole che la circondano. [Living marine shells of Sicily and surrounding islands]. *Atti dell'Accademia Gioenia di scienze naturali*, serie III, Vol. VI. Catania. Italian.
- Aversano F, Doneddu M, Manunza M, Graziani G, Micali P, Palazzi S. 1984. Malacofauna marina della Sardegna – area 154. [Marine malacofauna of Sardinia-area 154]. *Notiziario SIM*. 2(3-4):62–63. Italian.
- Bacallado JJ, Ortea J, Moro L, Martin-Barrios FJ, Cruz T, Mesa R. 2008.

- Inventario de los moluscos de la marina de Arrecife (Lanzarote). [Inventory of marine molluscs of Arrecife (Lanzarote)]. Informe Tecnico. Ayuntamiento de Arrecife. Spanish.
- Ballesteros M, Barrajon A, Luque AA, Moreno D, Talavera P, Templado J. 1986. Contribució al conocimiento de los gasteropodos marinos de Almería. [Contribution to the knowledge of marine gasteropods of Almería]. *Iberus*. 6(1):39–55. Spanish.
- Bellini R. 1929. I molluschi del Golfo di Napoli. [Molluscs of Naples gulf]. *Annuario del Museo Zoologico della Regia Università di Napoli, Nuova Serie*, vol. 6. Napoli. Italian.
- Berardelli B, Cosenza M, Cuomo M, Facente A, Fasulo G, Izzillo F, Perna E, Toscano F, Villari G. 1982. Malacofauna marina della Campania – area 042. [Marine malacofauna of Campania–area 042]. *Bollettino Malacologico*. 18(9-12):329–331. Italian.
- Berardelli B, Fasulo G. 1988. Malacofauna marina della Campania – area 043. [Marine malacofauna of Campania–area 043]. *Notiziario SIM*. 6(3-4):40. Italian.
- Bertozzi A, Biagi F, Biagi V, Cerri L, Gaglini A, Mannucci F, Miari E, Micali P, Poli D, Sbaragli F. 1984. Malacofauna marina della Toscana – area 024. [Marine malacofauna of Tuscany-area 024]. *Notiziario SIM*. 2(5-6):75–83. Italian.
- Bucquoy E, Dautzenberg P, Dollfus G. 1882. Les Mollusques Marins du Roussillon. [Marine Molluscs of Roussillon]. Paris: J.B. Baillièrre & fils. French.
- Cachia C, Mifsud C, Sammut PM. 1993. An Annotated Check-List of the Marine Mollusca of the Maltese Islands. *Erste Vorarlberger Malakologische Gesellschaft, Rankweil, Austria*.
- Coen G. 1937. Nuovo saggio di una Sylloge Molluscorum Adriaticorum. [New essay on Adriatic Molluscs collection]. *Memoria CCXL del Reggio Comitato Talassografico Italiano, Venezia*. Italian.
- Cossignani T, Ardevini R. 2011. Malacologia Mediterranea. *Atlante delle conchiglie del Mediterraneo*. [Mediterranean malacology. Atlas of the Mediterranean shells]. Ancona. L'Informatore Piceno. Italian.
- Cossignani T, Cossignani V, Di Nisio A, Passamonti M. 1992. *Atlante delle conchiglie del Medio Adriatico*. [Atlas of the shells in Middle Adriatic]. Ancona: L'Informatore Piceno. Italian.
- Costa O. 1829. *Catalogo sistematico e ragionato dei Testacei delle due Sicilie*. [Systematic and thoughtful catalog of Testacea of two Sicily]. Napoli: Tipografia della Minerva. Italian.
- Cuomo M, Facente A, Fasulo G, Izzillo F, Perna E, Toscano F, Villari G. 1983. Malacofauna marina della Campania – area 042. [Marine malacofauna of Campania -area 042]. *Notiziario SIM*. 1(3-4):38–40. Italian.
- D'Angelo G, Gargiullo S. 1978. *Guida alle Conchiglie mediterranee*. [Guide to the Mediterranean shells]. Milano: Fabri Edditori. Italian.
- De Chia MM. 1912. Aplech de noticies sobre 'ls Moluschs de Catalunya y catàlech provisional de ismate ixos. (Continuació). *Butlletí de la Institució Catalana d'Historia Natural Segona época*. 9(1):103–107. Spanish.
- Doneddu M, Manunza B. 1989. Note sul ritrovamento di alcuni molluschi poco frequenti per il litorale di Alghero. [Notes on findings of some rare molluscs for the cost of Alghero]. *Bollettino Malacologico*. 25(5-8):263–264. Italian.
- Dhora D. 2009. Mollusks of Albania. *Archives of Biological Sciences, Belgrade*. 61(3):537–553.
- Facente A, Izzillo F, Villani G. 1983. Malacofauna marina del Lazio. [Marine malacofauna of Lazio]. *Notiziario SIM*. 1(3-4):32. Italian.
- Federico A, Tripodi C. 1967. Itinerari malacologici campani: l'isola di Capri. [Malacological Itinerary of Campania: Capri island]. *Conchiglie*. 3(11-12):158–163. Italian.
- Fischer P. 1865. *Faune Conchyliologique marine de la Gironde et des côtes du Sud-Ouest de la France*. [Marine shells fauna of Gironde and south-west coast of France]. *Actes de la Societe Linneenne de Bordeaux*. 25:7–88. French.
- Fischer W. 2005. *Cabestana cutacea* (Linne 1767) (Gastropoda: Ranellidae), eine neue Art fur die griechische marine Mollusken fauna. [*Cabestana cutacea* (Linne 1767) (Gastropoda: Ranellidae), a new record for the Greek marine molluscs fauna]. *Club Conchylia Informatoren*. 37(1-2):59–61. German.
- Fretter V, Graham A. 1981. The Prosobranch Molluscs of Britain and Denmark. Part 6. *The Journal of Molluscan Study, supplement*. 9:285–363.
- Ghisotti F. 1978. Rinvenimenti malacologici nel Mediterraneo. [Malacological findings in the Mediterranean Sea]. *Segnalazioni del gruppo campano*, 2. *Conchiglie*. 14(9-10):151–166. Italian.
- Ghisotti F, Melone GC. 1968. *Cymatium (Cabestana) cutaceum* (Linnaeus, 1767). *Schede Malacologiche del Mediterraneo*. [*Cymatium (Cabestana) cutaceum* (Linnaeus, 1767)]. *Malacological lists of Mediterranean Sea* Società Malacologica Italiana. Serie 20Cb03: p. 6. Italian.
- Giannuzzi-Savelli R, Pusateri F, Palmeri A, Ebreo C. 1996. *Atlante delle conchiglie marine del Mediterraneo*. Vol. 2. [Atlas of the Mediterranean sea shells. Vol. 2]. Roma: La Conchiglia. Italian.
- Giribet G, Peñas A. 1997. Fauna malacológica del litoral del Garraf (NE de la Península Ibérica). [Malacological fauna of Gaffar coast (NE of Iberian peninsula)]. *Iberus*. 15(1):41–93. Spanish.
- Hidalgo JG. 1917. *Fauna malacologica de España, Portugal y las Baleares*. [Malacological fauna of Spain, Portugal and Balear islands]. Madrid. *Trabajos del Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, serie Zoología*, 30. Spanish.
- Jeffreys JG. 1856. On the Marine Testacea of the Piedmontese Coasts. *Annals & magazine of natural history*. 2nd ser. 17:155–188.
- Jeffreys JG. 1863. *British Conchology, or an account of the Mollusca which now inhabit the British isles and the surrounding seas*. London: J. van Voorst.
- Koukouras A. 2010. Check-list of marine species from Greece. Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. Assembled in the framework of the EU FP7 PESI project. [Internet] [cited 2013 May 5]; Available from: <http://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=sourcedetails&id=149096>
- Locard A. 1886. *Catalogue Général des Mollusques vivants de France, Mollusques Marins*. [General catalog of living Molluscs of the France, Marine Molluscs]. Lyon-Paris: J.B. Baillièrre & fils. French.
- Locard A. 1892. *Les Coquilles Marines des Côtes de France*. [Marine shells of the French coast]. Paris: J.B. Baillièrre & fils. French.
- Lugli A, Micali P, Repetto G. 1984. Malacofauna marina della Liguria – area 014. [Marine malacofauna of Liguria -area 014]. *Notiziario SIM*. 2(7-8):105–107. Italian.
- Lugli A, Palazzi S. 1987. Malacofauna marina della Sicilia – area 048. [Marine malacofauna of Sicily -area 048]. *Notiziario SIM*. 5(3-4):64–65. Italian.
- Luque AA. 1986. Contribució al conocimiento de los gasteropodos de las costas de Malaga y Granada. [Contribution to the knowledge of gasteropods on the coast of Malaga and Granada]. *Iberus*. 6(1):79–94. Spanish.
- Mannucci F. 1983. Malacofauna marina della Sicilia – area 143. [Marine malacofauna of Sicily -area 143]. *Notiziario SIM*. 1(7-8):34–36. Italian.
- Mannucci F, Giannuzzi-Savelli R, Palmeri A. 1983. [Malacofauna marina della Sicilia – area 141]. *Notiziario SIM*. 1(7-8):40–42. Italian.
- Maravigna C. 1839. *Mémoires pour servir à l'histoire naturelle de la Sicile*. [Memories of natural historie of Sicily]. Paris: Baillièrre. French.
- Merella P, Porcheddu S, Casu S. 1994. La malacofauna della riserva naturale di Scandola (Corsica nord-occidentale). [Malacofauna of Scandola nature reserve (Corsica nord-west)]. *Bollettino Malacologico*. 30(5-9):111–128. Italian.
- Miari E, Graziani C. 1984. Malacofauna marina della Sardegna – area 153. [Marine malacofauna of Sardinia -area 153]. *Notiziario SIM*. 2(3-4):61–62. Italian.
- Micali P, Russotti C, Villari A, Palazzi S. 1987. Malacofauna marina della Sicilia – area 142. [Marine malacofauna of Sicily]. *Notiziario SIM*. 5(3-4):63. Italian.
- Moro L, Martín JL, Garrido MJ, Izquierdo I, editors. 2003. *Lista de especies marinas de Canarias (algas, hongos, plantas y animales)* [List of Canary marine species (algae, mushrooms, plants and animals)]. 2003. *Consejería de Política Territorial y Medio Ambiente del Gobierno de Canarias*. Spanish.

- Negra O, Lipparini G Z. 2005. I molluschi e le loro conchiglie. [Molluscs and their shells]. Roma: Muzio Editore. Italian.
- Nobre A. 1937. Moluscos testaceos marinhos do arquipélago da Madeira. [Marine testaceous molluscs of Madeira archipelago]. Memórias e estudos do Museo zoologico da Universidade de Coimbra. Spanish.
- Nobre A. 1938. Fauna Malacologica de Portugal. [Malacological fauna of Portugal]. Porto. Portuguese.
- Nordsieck F, Garcia-Talavera F. 1979. Moluscos marinos de Canarias y Madeira (Gastropoda). [Marine molluscs of Canary and Madeira islands (Gastropoda)]. Aulade Cultura de Tenerife, Cabildo Insular de Tenerife. Spanish.
- Oliverio M. 2008. Gastropoda Prosobranchia. In: Relini G, editor. Checklist della flora e della fauna dei mari italiani. [Checklist of Italian marine flora and fauna]. Biologia Marina Mediterranea, Vol. 15 suppl. 1:235–278.
- Oriolo G. 1974. Conchiglie del litorale brindisino. [Shells on coast of Brindisi]. Brindisii res. 6:15–27. Italian.
- Ozturk B, Buzzurro G, AvniBenli H. 2003. Marine molluscs from Cyprus: new data and checklist. Bollettino Malacologico. 39(5-8):49–78.
- Pallary MG. 1920. Exploration scientifique du Maroc. [Scientific exploration of Morocco]. Fasc. 2, Malacologie. Rabat-Paris. French.
- Pallary P. 1900. Coquilles marines du littoral du departement d'Oran. [Marine shells of the coast of Oran]. Journal de Conchyliologie. 4(2):211–422. French.
- Pasteur-Humbert C. 1962. Les mollusques marins testacés du Maroc. [Marine testaceous molluscs of Morocco]. Rabat. Spanish.
- Payraudeau BC. 1826. Catalogue descriptif et méthodique des Annelides et des Mollusques de l'île de Corse. [Descriptive and methodical catalog of Annelides and Molluscs of the Corsica island]. Paris. French.
- Perretti E. 1984. Malacofauna marina della Basilicata – area 051. [Marine malacofauna of Basilicata -area 051]. Notiziario SIM. 2(1-2):29–30. Italian.
- Philippi RA. 1836. Enumeratio Molluscorum Siciliae, cum viventium, tum intellure tertiaria fossilium, quae in itinere suo observavit auctor. Berolini. Latin.
- Poppe GT, Goto Y. 1991. European Seashells, Vol. 1., Verlag C. Hemmen, Wiesbaden.
- Rebora C. 1986. Malacofauna marina della Liguria – area 011. [Marine malacofauna of Liguria -area 011]. Notiziario SIM. 4(3-4):48–49. Italian.
- Requien E. 1848. Catalogue des Coquilles de l'île de Corse. [Shells catalogue of Corsica island]. Avignon. French.
- Risso A. 1826. Histoire naturelle des principales productions de l'Europe méridionale et particulièrement de celles des environs de Nice et des Alpes Maritimes. [Natural history of south Europe and specially of Nice and Alpes Marines environment]. Paris. F.G. Levrault. Vol. 3: XVI, 1–480, 14 pls. French.
- RolanMosquera E. 1983. Molluscos de la Ria de Vigo. 1. Gasteropodos. [Molluscs of Ria de Vigo.1. Gasteropods]. Thalassas, 1 (1) Anexo 1:1–383. Spanish.
- Ruscoe C. A 2007. New record of *Cymatium cutaceum* in the UK! Pallidula. 37(2):12–13.
- Sabelli B, Spada G. 1978. Guida illustrata all'identificazione delle conchiglie del Mediterraneo. No. 11, Cassidae, Cymatidae I. [Illustrative guide for identification of Mediterranean shells. No. 11, Cassidae, Cymatidae I]. pp. 4. Supplemento a Conchiglie. 14(9-10). Italian.
- Salas C, Luque A. 1986. Contribución al conocimiento de los moluscos marinos de la Isla de Alboran. [Contribution to the knowledge of marine molluscs of Alboran island]. Iberus. 6(1):29–37. Spanish.
- Saunders GD. 1980. A reconciliation of available information on the Superfamily Cymatiacea in the waters around Europe, in Mediterranean Sea and the Eastern Atlantic Ocean. La Conchiglia. 12(134-135):3–10.
- Scacchi A. 1836. Catalogus Conchyliorum regni Neapolitani, quaeus que ad adhuc reperit. Napoli. Latin.
- Scuderi D. 2000. Contributo alla conoscenza dei vermetidae mediterranei: *Vermetus (Thylaeodus) granulatus* (Gravenhorst, 1831) e suoi principali morfotipi. [Contribution to the knowledge of Mediterranean vermetidae: *Vermetus (Thylaeodus) granulatus* (Gravenhorst, 1831) and their basic morphotips]. Bollettino Malacologico. 35(1-4):45–48. Italian.
- Segers W, Swinnen F, Abreu A. 2009. An annotated checklist of the marine molluscs from the archipelagos of Madeira and the Selvagens (NE Atlantic Ocean). Bocagiana. 226:1–60.
- Settepassi F. 1970. Atlante malacologico dei molluschi marini viventi nel Mediterraneo Vol. 1. [Malacological atlas of living marine molluscs in Mediterranean Sea, Vol. 1.]. Roma. Museo di Zoologia del Comunedì Roma. Italian.
- Sileu M, Sosso M. 1987. Malacofauna marina della Sardegna – area 152. [Marine malacofauna of Sardinia -area 152]. Notiziario SIM. 5(3-4):65–67. Italian.
- Smriglio C, Mariottini P, Gravina F. 1989. Molluschi del Mar Tirreno centrale: ritrovamento di *Umbraculum mediterraneum* (Lamarck, 1819) e osservazioni in acquario. Contributo VII. [Molluscs of central Tirenian Sea: findings of *Umbraculum mediterraneum* (Lamarck, 1819) and observation in aquarium]. Bollettino Malacologico. 25(9-12):329–334. Italian.
- Soppelsa O, Crocetta F, Fasulo G. 2007. I molluschi marini di Punta di Pioppeto (Isola di Procida–Campania). [Marine molluscs of Punta di Pioppeto (Procida island–Campania)]. Bollettino Malacologico. 43(1-8):21–32. Italian.
- Sorbi E, Terzer G. 1982. Malacofauna marina della Liguria – area 013. [Marine malacologia of Liguria -area 013]. Bollettino Malacologico. 18(9-12):327. Italian.
- Spano C, Puddu B, Murgia D. 2002. Autoecologia e ambiente dei molluschi marini alloctoni raccolti in spiagge delle coste meridionale e sud-orientale della Sardegna. [Autecologia and environment of marine allochthonous molluscs collected on the beaches of the south and south-east Sardinia]. Rendiconti seminario facoltà scienze università di Cagliari. 72(2):29–65. Italian.
- Stjepčević J. 1967. Makro-Mollusca Bokokotorskog zaliva [Macro-Molluscs of the Boka Kotorska Bay]. Studia Marina. 2:3–67 Serbian.
- Stjepčević J, Parenzan P. 1980. Il Golfo delle Bocche di Cattaro–condizioni generali e biocenosi bentoniche con carta ecologica delle due baie interne: di Kotor (Cattaro) e di Risan (Risano). [Boka kotorska Bay -general characteristics and composition of the benthic biocenosis with ecological map of Kotor's and Risan's Bay]. Studia Marina. 9-10:3–145. Italian.
- Tapparone-Canefri C. 1869. Indice sistematico dei Molluschi Testacei dei dintorni di Spezia e del suo Golfo. [Systematic list of Testaceous Molluscs from surrounding of Spezia and its gulf]. Atti della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali. 12:261–406. Italian.
- Tarruella Ruestes A, López Soriano J. 2006. Moluscos marinos del Baix Camp (Tarragona, NE Península Ibérica). [Marine Molluscs of Baix Camp (Tarragona, NE Iberian peninsula)]. Spira. 2(1):1–16. Spanish.
- Toscano F, Cretella M. 1991. SEM observations on the protoconchs of some Mediterranean Ranellidae (Gastropoda: Tonnoidea). Bollettino Malacologico. 27(5-9):101–106.
- Trigo JE, Otero Schmitt JJ. 1987. Contribución al conocimiento de los moluscos marinos de la Ria de Pontevedra e Isla de Ons. [Contribution to the knowledge of marine molluscs from Ria de Pontevedra e Isla de Ons]. Iberus. 7(1):121–128. Spanish.
- Trono D. 2006. Nuovi dati sulla malacofauna del Salento (Puglia meridionale). [New data on malacofauna of Salento (south Puglia)]. Bollettino Malacologico. 42(5-8):58–84. Italian.
- Vazzana A. 2010. La malacofauna del circolitorale di Scilla (Stretto di Messina). [Malacofauna from the circolithoral of Scilla (Messina strait)]. Bollettino Malacologico. 46(2):65–74. Italian.
- Vial P. 1988. La malacofaune marine des environs de Martigues. (F. Bouches du Rhone). [Marine malacofauna of Martinic environment (F. Bouches du Rhone)]. Apex (Brusseles). 3(1):21–37. French.